

SPECTRUM USAGE MEASUREMENTS IN POTENTIAL PCS FREQUENCY BANDS

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Abstract - Spectrum usage measurements were made in several potential Personal Communication Services (PCS) frequency bands in the 600 to 2600 MHz range in five U.S. cities. Geographic dependence (within a city) of spectrum usage was determined for all of the cities. Measurements were made using a mobile, computer-controlled, automated radio frequency measurement system that was installed in a minivan. The raw data taken at each site consisted of received signal levels for each frequency measured. These were processed to provide signal level and measured band usage graphs. The heaviest usage for all cities was seen in the 869-894 MHz (cellular base station-to-mobile) band and the 864-868 MHz (SMR) band. The frequency bands showing the least usage in all cities were the 901-902 MHz (GPMRS), 1850-1990 MHz (Private Fixed Microwave), and the 2400-2483.5 MHz (ISM and Part 15) bands.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Institute for Telecommunication Sciences (ITS) and Telesis Technology Laboratory, Inc. (TTL), a subsidiary of Pacific Telesis Group, have entered into a cooperative research agreement under the provisions of the Federal Technology Transfer Act (FTTA) of 1986. As part of this agreement, ITS conducted spectrum usage measurements in several potential PCS frequency bands in the 600 to 2600 MHz range in five cities in the United States. The spectrum usage measurements over this frequency range will provide information to assist the FCC in determining what frequency bands are suitable for PCS and whether PCS can share spectrum with current users.

2. OBJECTIVES AND MEASUREMENT STRATEGY

The basic objective in the spectrum usage measurements was to determine the relative degree of current spectrum usage for all frequency bands listed in Table 1.

A complete characterization of spectrum usage would require a measurement program sufficiently extensive to provide significant information on time and location statistics. Because of the need to constrain the size of the measurement

Table 1. Individual Frequency Bands Grouped According to Service

Frequency Range	Type of Service
614-806 MHz	UHF-TV
824-849 MHz 869-894 MHz	Cellular
849-851 MHz 894-896 MHz	Air-to-ground
864-868 MHz	Specialized Mobile Radio (SMR)
901-902 MHz 930-931 MHz 940-941 MHz	General Purpose Mobile Radio Service (GPMRS)
902-928 MHz	Industrial, Scientific, and Medical (ISM), Part 15, Automatic Vehicle Location, Amateur Radio
1850-1990 MHz	Private Fixed Microwave
2110-2130 MHz 2160-2180 MHz	Common Carrier Fixed Microwave
2400-2483.5 MHz	ISM, Part 15

effort, the measurement program was designed to acquire the information that seemed to be most important. To provide information that would help determine which frequency bands show potential for PCS and which bands show no potential, it was concluded that geographic factors would be more important than temporal factors in the measurements.

Therefore, the measurements were designed to provide an extensive sampling of various geographic locations, using a measurement system that would encounter radio signals in about the same way that future PCS users would.

Measurements were taken in five cities: Dallas, Chicago, New York, Los Angeles, and San Francisco. Sites in each city were selected at the intersection points and center point of

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a 6×6 square grid with five mile spacing between grid lines. This yielded a total of 37 measurement sites per city.

The measurements were made exclusively outdoors with a small van, using an omnidirectional vertically polarized rooftop antenna. Due to the large number of sites per city, it was only possible to make measurements at each site for about 30 minutes. This, while not allowing enough time to develop good temporal statistics on the received signals at each site, still accomplished the objective of providing good statistics of the geographic variability. The 14 individual frequency bands listed in Table 1 were grouped into five measurement frequency bands in order to be measured in a uniform and efficient manner. The five measurement frequency bands were: 614-806 MHz, 824-944 MHz, 1850-1994 MHz, 2110-2182 MHz, and 2400-2600 MHz.

Ideally, one would like to make measurements with a bandwidth as close as possible to the bandwidth of the PCS system. Since that bandwidth was not known, the selection of measurement parameters was made to cover the range of likely bandwidths and to show as much as possible about the actual use of the spectrum. Three sets of measurement parameters were used to make the measurements:

- narrowband: 10 kHz bandwidth, 3 kHz video filter, sampling detector
- wideband: 300 kHz bandwidth, 10 kHz video filter, sampling detector
- peak: 300 kHz bandwidth, 3000 kHz video filter, peak detector.

The data presented in this paper were taken using the narrowband parameters since they provide the most detailed information and the best measurement sensitivity.

3. MEASUREMENT SYSTEM

Measurements were made with a mobile, computer-controlled, automated measurement system that measures rf signals in the 600-2600 MHz frequency range. A block diagram of the Spectrum Usage Measurement System¹ is shown in Figure 1. A wideband vertically polarized omnidirectional antenna with an average gain of 0 dBi (measured) is used. The computer controls the four-port coaxial switch based on the frequency range to be measured. For measurements between 1500 and 2600 MHz, the rf signal goes through the discrete bandpass filter and amplifier. The rf preselector is bypassed, the signal travels through the second amplifier, and is measured by the spectrum analyzer. For measurements between 600 and 1500 MHz, the rf signal bypasses the discrete bandpass filter and amplifier and goes through the YIG filter and amplifier in the rf preselector. The

signal then passes through the second amplifier and is measured by the spectrum analyzer.

The measurement system is controlled by a portable computer via the GPIB bus. A 44MB Bernoulli disk drive is used to store the data.

4. CALIBRATION

A noise diode calibration procedure was performed twice a day. The procedure consisted of manually disconnecting the antenna feed cable at the antenna output connector and manually connecting a 25 dB ENR noise diode to the end of the antenna feed cable. The Y-factor method (using on and off noise diode power) was used to measure system noise figure and system gain over the entire 600-2600 MHz range. The system noise figure and system gain (calibration curves) were compared to the initial calibration curves of the system to determine if the system was operating properly. If the system was operating properly, the calibration curves were saved to disk. For the 600 to 1000 MHz range, the typical system noise figure was 12 to 13 dB while the gain was approximately 36 dB. For the 1850 to 2600 MHz range, the typical system noise figure was 8 to 10 dB while the gain varied from about 28 to 38 dB.

The antenna system test was performed once daily before measurements commenced. This procedure entailed mounting a short monopole calibration antenna on the roof of the mini-van a fixed distance away from the omnidirectional receive antenna. A low level comb generator signal with harmonics between 600 and 2400 MHz was transmitted through the calibration antenna. Received signal level (RSL) vs frequency was measured and compared to a baseline antenna system test plot (RSL vs frequency) that was made during system development testing. The antenna system test was used exclusively to verify that the antenna and bulkhead connector cabling were working properly and was primarily qualitative in nature. Large differences in RSL seen between the present and baseline antenna system test plots would point to a malfunction or degradation in the antenna itself or the bulkhead connector cabling.

5. DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The raw data taken at each site within a city consisted of RSLs (in dBm) for each frequency measured. The data

¹ Certain commercial equipment, instruments, or materials are identified in this paper to specify adequately the technical aspects of the reported results. In no case does such identification imply recommendation or endorsement by the National Telecommunications and Information Administration, nor does it imply that the material or equipment identified is necessarily the best available for the purpose.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the Spectrum Usage Measurement System.

analysis entailed processing these raw data to develop three different types of statistics: signal level, measured frequency usage, and measured band usage. In this paper, a few examples of the signal level and measured band usage statistics are presented in graphical form. A detailed presentation of the data is given in [1].

5.1 Signal level

The signal level graphs show RSLs across an entire measurement frequency band. These plots show minimum, maximum, and mean signal levels at each frequency as measured at all sites within an individual city. These graphs are qualitative in nature; they give a strong impression as to how the signals are grouped in the band and whether the usage is heavy, random, etc.

The signal level graphs from Dallas are presented in Figure 2 for each of the five measurement frequency bands: 614-806 MHz, 824-944 MHz, 1850-1994 MHz, 2110-2182 MHz, and 2400-2600 MHz. Figure 2(a) shows the signal level graph for the 614-806 MHz (UHF-TV) band. Looking at the maximum RSL, it is clear that five strong UHF-TV transmitters were observed in the Dallas measurements. Only four strong UHF-TV transmitters are detectable from the mean RSL curve; channel 55 (716-722 MHz) does not show up on the mean RSL curve. This suggests that channel 55 was received at only a few of the sites probably because it operates only a few hours a day. It is evident that some intermodulation distortion from the video and audio carriers of the UHF-TV signals has occurred. The only band in the measured data where intermodulation distortion was readily apparent was in the UHF-TV band.

Investigating the signal level graph in Figure 2(b), the maximum RSL curve shows much activity and strong signals for the 824-849 MHz, 851-866 MHz, 869-894 MHz, 929-932 MHz, and 935-940 MHz frequency ranges. The mean RSL curve suggests that each signal detected in the 824-849 MHz band was received at only a few of the sites.

Figure 2(c) shows the signal level graph for the 1850-1994 MHz band. Looking at the maximum RSL, it appears that a few broadband and several narrowband signals were detected. The highest amplitude signal received in this band was -90 dBm. Since the mean RSL curve shows much lower amplitude signals than the maximum RSL curve, it suggests that each detected signal was present at most at a few sites.

From the maximum RSL curve of the signal level graph in Figure 2(d), it is clear that in the 2110-2182 MHz band, like the 1850-1994 MHz band, only a few broadband and several narrowband signals were detected. The maximum RSL never exceeded -85 dBm. As in the 1850-1994 MHz band, the mean RSL curve shows much lower amplitude signals than the maximum RSL curve. This, of course, suggests that each detected signal was received at only a few sites.

Examining the maximum RSL curve of the signal level graph in Figure 2(e) shows what appears to be a wideband signal around 2400 MHz and many narrowband signals. The mean RSL curve suggests that the narrowband signals from 2500-2600 MHz were present at a considerable number of sites and that each signal seen outside of this frequency range was detected at only a few sites.

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Figure 2. Signal level plots for Dallas.

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5.2 Measured band usage

The band usage statistics for all five cities are summarized by a bar graph for each individual frequency band. Each bar graph shows the minimum percentage of the band unused² at 50%, 90%, and 100% of the sites in each of the five cities. These cities are denoted on the bar graph as DA (Dallas), CH (Chicago), NY (New York), LA (Los Angeles), and SF (San Francisco). The 100% number may be thought of as the percentage of the band that was unused at the busiest site. The 90% number is the percentage of the band unused at the busiest site after the busiest 10% of the sites have been eliminated. The 50% number is the percentage of the band unused at the typical (median) site (i.e., it is the percentage of the band unused at the busiest site after the busiest 50% of the sites have been eliminated). Note that 83% of the band unused at 100% of the sites does not mean that the same 83% of the frequencies were unused at all sites. It means that no less than 83% of the frequencies were unused at each site.

Additionally, each bar graph includes averaged data over all of the cities. Three separate averages are computed: the "50% all-cities average", "90% all-cities average", and "100% all-cities average". These averages are computed by taking the minimum percentage of the band unused (for 50%, 90% and 100% of the sites respectively) in each city individually (as described in the preceding paragraph) and averaging over all five cities.

The frequency bands showing the highest usage were the 864-868 MHz (SMR) and the 869-894 MHz (cellular base station-to-mobile) bands.

Studying the measured band usage bar graph in Figure 3 (the 864-868 MHz band) shows that the busiest sites in each city had only about 1% of the band unused. Note that the 90% all-cities average shows a minimum of 42% of the band unused. This indicates that within each city a few sites showed significantly higher usage than the other sites. The reason that this occurs can be explained by looking at the example signal level graph from Dallas for the 824-944 MHz band. Observing the maximum RSL curve in Figure 2(b) over the 864-868 MHz range, it is apparent that either transmitter noise sidebands or intermodulation distortion was present. Since these noise sidebands/intermodulation products are above the -115 dBm threshold, it causes an apparent high usage. Since the mean RSL curves are not affected much, it can be deduced that these noise sidebands/intermodulation products were detected at most at only a few sites.

Measured band usage in each city for the 869-894 MHz band (cellular base station-to-mobile) is portrayed in Figure 4. The 100% all-cities average shows a minimum of only 3% of the band unused. The 50% all-cities average shows a minimum of 33% of the band unused.

Figure 3. Measured band usage for all cities in the 864-868 MHz band.

Figure 4. Measured band usage for all cities in the 869-894 MHz band.

The frequency bands showing the lowest usage were the 901-902 MHz (GPMRS), 1850-1990 MHz (Private Fixed Microwave), and 2400-2483.5 MHz (ISM and Part 15) bands.

From the measured band usage graph for the 901-902 MHz band shown in Figure 5, the 100% all-cities average shows a minimum of 93% of the band unused.

Figure 5. Measured band usage for all cities in the 901-902 MHz band.

² For the purposes of this paper, the percentage of frequency band (or band) unused means the percentage of frequencies in the band whose RSLs never exceeded -115 dBm during the measurements. A high percentage of the band unused is not an indication of the likelihood of a regulatory allocation change.

Observing the usage in the 1850-1990 MHz band, shown in Figure 6, the busiest site out of all sites in all cities shows 88% of the band unused. The 50% all-cities average shows a minimum of 99% of the band unused.

Figure 6. Measured band usage for all cities in the 1850-1990 MHz band.

Figure 7 demonstrates the usage in the 2400-2483.5 MHz band. The 100% all-cities average shows a minimum of 96% of the band unused.

Figure 7. Measured band usage for all cities in the 2400-2483.5 MHz band.

6. SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

This paper discussed the objectives and measurement strategy for making the spectrum usage measurements in several potential PCS frequency bands. The measurement system was described along with the calibration procedures used. Several examples of the results from the data analysis were presented. In particular, a few signal level and band usage graphs were shown.

When considering the band usage results, several factors that affect apparent spectrum usage must be kept in mind. The percentage of the band unused was determined from the data that used the narrowband measurement parameters (10 kHz bandwidth, 3 kHz video filter, sampling detector). Communications systems whose receivers operate using the same parameters should expect to see the same spectrum being used. For receivers operating with different bandwidths, the amount of spectrum being used would appear different. Wider

bandwidth systems would see a higher apparent spectrum usage. The -115 dBm threshold was used to present the band usage results. By using higher thresholds, less usage would be shown. The measurements made in this experiment indicate spectrum usage as determined by reception of transmitted signals. No provision was made to determine additional frequency use that could be prohibited by potential interference from a PCS system to existing receivers. Since the measurements in this experiment were made exclusively outdoors, PCS systems operating indoors would see higher usage than that indicated from these measurements in the bands with indoor transmitters (such as the ISM and Part 15 bands). Finally, since a vertically polarized antenna was used for the measurements, horizontally polarized signals appeared weaker than they actually were. If horizontally polarized signals had been received with a horizontally polarized antenna, the apparent usage would have been higher.

REFERENCES

- [1] Wepman, J.A., R.J. Matheson, K.C. Allen, and R.J. Achatz (1991), Spectrum usage measurements in potential PCS frequency bands, NTIA Report 91-279, September, 153 pp. (NTIS Order No. PB 92-123819/AS).